

MOBIL ADDIKSIYANING PSIXOPROFILAKTIKASI YO'NALISHIDA TRENINGLAR VA
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USE OF TRAININGS AND PRACTICAL EXERCISES IN THE PSYCHOPROPHYLAXIS
OF MOBILE ADDICTION

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Annotatsiya: Mobil addiksiya (smartfon yoki mobil qurilma addiksiyasi) zamonaviy jamiyatning dolzarb muammosi bo'lib, ayniqsa, yoshlar va o'smirlar orasida keng tarqalgan. Bu addiksiya ruhiy salomatlikka salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi, masalan, stress, depressiya va uyqu buzilishiga olib keladi. Psixoprofilaktika (oldini olish) yo'nalishida treninglar va amaliy mashqlar muhim rol o'ynaydi, chunki ular shaxsiy chidamlilikni oshirish, o'z-o'zini boshqarish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish va addiksiya alomatlarini kamaytirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: mobil addiksiya, psixoprofilaktika, trening, qaramlik, tobelik, psixologik immunitet, psixologik himoya mexanizmlari.

Annotation: Mobile addiction (smartphone or mobile device addiction) is a pressing issue in modern society, especially widespread among youth and adolescents. This type of addiction negatively affects mental health, leading to conditions such as stress, depression, and sleep disorders. Trainings and practical exercises play an important role in psychoprophylaxis (prevention), as they help enhance personal resilience, develop self-regulation skills, and reduce the symptoms of addiction.

Keywords: mobile addiction, psychoprophylaxis, training, addiction, dependency, psychological immunity, psychological defense mechanisms.

Introduction

According to sociological research data, the active users of modern smartphones are primarily young people aged 19 to 35. They belong to social groups ranging from the lower boundary of the middle class to higher-income strata and actively use modern information and communication technologies. These users are distinguished by their extensive use of the latest achievements in consumer electronics, including mobile devices, wearable electronics, and internet services. They are active users of social networks, blogging platforms, and various digital communication services, and they are also interested in new technologies and internet startups in the global information space. As a result of constant interaction with foreign internet resources, most of them possess at least a basic level of English proficiency. Typically, such users live in economically and socially stable regions, mainly in large cities.

Adult individuals perceive mobile phones as an essential means of communication in modern life. However, among young military personnel, excessive attachment or psychological dependence on mobile devices may be observed. In some cases, the mobile phone occupies an overly significant place in a person's life and becomes an almost indispensable attribute for a serviceman. As a result,

mobile technologies can have a substantial impact on the psychological state of young military personnel and, in certain cases, may lead to negative consequences. Therefore, the issue of “young serviceman – mobile phone” is considered one of the important socio-psychological problems that requires attention not only from command and educational structures but also from the servicemen themselves. [1].

The concept of “addiction” is considered one of the most multifaceted and complex categories in the fields of psychology and medicine. The English word “addiction” can be translated as inclination, habituation, or dependence. This concept was introduced into medical practice in 1964 by the Expert Committee of the World Health Organization, after which it began to be used alongside terms such as pathological craving characteristic of disease, harmful habit, drug addiction, and alcoholism. According to the World Health Organization, addiction is interpreted as a state of periodic or chronic intoxication caused by the repeated consumption of a natural or synthetic substance. Therefore, initially this term was used in a narrow sense, mainly to describe chemical dependencies related to medications, tobacco, alcohol, and narcotic substances.

This narrow interpretation was also supported by M. Cordwell, who explains addiction as a type of personality disorder in which a person is unable to make even the simplest decisions independently, and therefore feels the need for help or support from others, while perceiving themselves as helpless and insufficiently capable.

In a broader sense, the concept of addiction is characterized by a person’s need for a particular object or individual, an inability to function without them, or even an inability to imagine their existence without them. In such cases, an individual develops a strong and persistent desire to perform certain actions or engage in specific activities. People who become excessively devoted to something or someone are referred to as addicts. When translated from English, this term can also mean an enthusiast, devotee, or fan of a particular interest. In scientific literature, the concept of “addict” is generally used in two meanings: first, to describe individuals who are unable to stop consuming various substances, and second, to characterize people who devote all their free time to a particular activity.

D. R. Meers interprets addiction as a “consequence of the disruption of the normal state,” thereby further expanding the meaning of this concept and bringing it closer to deviant behavior. The Latin term “deviatio” means deviation or departure from the norm. Similarly, L. M. Dodds evaluates addiction as a pathological form of activity that does not correspond to normative behavior and explains it as a compulsively driven activity characterized by high intensity and stability. During such activity, the individual’s “self” system loses its relative autonomy, while the ability to adapt to real situations and mechanisms of self-control are significantly weakened. This approach has considerably broadened the scope of the concept of addiction, making it applicable not only to substance-related (chemical) dependencies but also to behavioral (non-chemical) addictions.

A. W. Shaef proposed one of the shortest and most general definitions of addiction, interpreting it as “any process that a person cannot control.” This scholar was among the first to distinguish, alongside chemical addictions, non-chemical or process addictions. Chemical addictions include those related to alcohol, drugs, tobacco, and food. Non-chemical or behavior-based addictions, in turn, include excessive preoccupation with saving money, gambling, sexual activity, overworking, excessive use of the internet, or excessive involvement in religious activities.

The multifactorial origin of non-chemical addiction has led to the need to distinguish its primary and intermediate types. According to the classification proposed by T. P. Korolenko and N. V. Dmitriyeva, primary behavioral addictions include gambling, dependence on interpersonal relationships, escape addiction, sexual addiction, love addiction, addiction associated with a constant feeling of lack of time, work addiction, and excessive spending. Intermediate types of addiction include those related to food, such as overeating or starvation.

Young military personnel who have just begun their service are in the process of personal development and professional adaptation, and therefore their level of psychological stability may not yet be sufficiently formed. For this reason, they may be prone to excessive inclination or addiction to digital communication tools, particularly the use of mobile phones. According to experts, the more time a person spends in virtual communication, the more complicated their real social interactions may become, including direct communication with peers and fellow servicemen. While this issue was previously discussed in connection with the increasing number of personal computers connected to the internet, the widespread use of mobile phones has turned it into an even more pressing socio-psychological problem. This is because mobile devices are constantly with the individual and provide continuous access to the global network. As a result, some young military personnel may fail to sufficiently develop real-life social communication skills and may experience difficulties in open communication within a team or in establishing new social connections.

The problem of mobile phone addiction, referred to as nomophobia (from the English term “no mobile phone phobia”), has been widely discussed in psychological research in recent years. Today, due to the widespread use of mobile phones among the majority of the population in developed countries, this condition is becoming a common socio-psychological phenomenon. Nomophobia describes a psychological state in which a mobile phone becomes an integral part of a person’s life, creating a constant need to stay connected to it. In such situations, individuals frequently check their mobile phones, make calls or send messages even without necessity, and are often unable to clearly explain the reasons for these behaviors. The mobile phone is perceived as an important psychological support in a person’s daily life, and separation from it may cause feelings of anxiety, discomfort, or emotional instability [2].

An analysis of psychological literature on this issue shows that the development of mobile phone addiction may be interconnected with a number of individual psychological characteristics. In particular, a tendency toward addictive behavior, level of intellectual development, communicative qualities, indicators of conformism, and the adequacy of self-esteem may all play an important role in the formation of mobile phone addiction. Based on this, the present study advances a scientific hypothesis that there is a statistically significant relationship between the level of mobile phone addiction and the aforementioned psychological indicators of an individual.

Considering the relevance of the problem and its importance in shaping the psychological climate within military units and ensuring the effective social adaptation of personnel, the main objective of this study is to theoretically analyze the psychological factors contributing to the development of mobile phone addiction and, on the basis of empirical research, to identify the specific characteristics of this phenomenon among young military servicemen.

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